

Name: Andreas Nikiforiadis^{1*}, Socrates Basbas²

Organisation:

¹Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, Hellenic Institute of Transport, 6th km Charilaou – Thermi Rd., Thessaloniki 57001, Greece

²Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, School of Rural and Surveying Engineering, AUTH Campus, Thessaloniki 54124, Greece

E-Mail address: anikiforiadis@certh.gr

PEDESTRIANS-CYCLISTS SHARED SPACES: ANALYSIS OF INTERACTIONS AND ATTITUDES

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INTRODUCTION

Shared streets and spaces, i.e. the coexistence of different categories of users in a single infrastructure, is not a new concept. On the contrary, streets traditionally have been a place of interaction between people, where the social, cultural and economic life of cities took place (Hamilton-Baillie, 2008). However, the evolution of the automotive industry and the rapid introduction of motor vehicles in the transportation systems over the last century have created new challenges and the priority in transportation and urban planning was given to serve greater volumes of motorized traffic and achieve higher speeds for the vehicles. This planning gradually contributed to the separation of different categories of road users and to the tendency of rendering exclusive lanes to each one of them, giving priority to motor vehicles (Hamilton-Baillie, 2008). The first attempts to rearrange streets and integrate traffic into social space were made in the late 1960s by Dutch scientists (Hass-Klau, 1990). Today there is a tendency to redistribute the urban environment in favour of pedestrians and “soft” transport modes, as well as to turn streets into places of activity and interaction of people, as expressed in the guidelines for the implementation of Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (Rupprecht Consult, 2019). In this direction, more and more cities are implementing shared infrastructures.

For the successful design and management of the infrastructures used by pedestrians, cyclists or both categories of users, the application of appropriate methodologies for assessment is required (Amprasi et al., 2020). For this reason, various evaluation metrics have been developed; some of them refer to pedestrians (e.g. walkability index, walkscore), while others refer to cyclists (e.g. bicycle safety index rating, bicycle environmental quality index) (Carter et al., 2006; Rodriguez-Valencia et al., 2020). However, the two most established metrics are the level of service (LOS) and the quality of service (QOS). The concept of LOS is very closely linked to the density of users in the infrastructure. Thus, LOS A, which is the ideal condition for the user, expresses a state of low user density and speed equal to that in free flow conditions, while LOS F expresses an unfavourable situation, where saturation conditions have occurred. Based on the above, it is understood that an infrastructure with a high LOS is not necessarily a well-designed infrastructure that offers satisfactory levels of safety and comfort (Sisiopiku et al., 2007). On the other hand, according to the Highway Capacity Manual (HCM) (TRB, 2010), the QOS describes whether an infrastructure works well, from the perspective of the users and therefore the concept of QOS extends to that of LOS.

In this paper, a holistic methodological framework for assessing pedestrians-cyclists shared infrastructure is developed. The methodological framework consists of two main parts, where the one deals with the investigation of LOS and the second with the perceived QOS. The aim of the methodological framework is to provide guidance to engineers, researchers and policy-makers, but also to give them the possibility to easily apply it or to adapt it in their needs.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous surveys have been carried out with the aim of investigating the pedestrian LOS and formulating appropriate methodologies. These methodologies utilize field measurements, interviews with experts and questionnaires, while most of them use statistical modelling or scoring system techniques, where score is being given in several infrastructure attributes. According to a recent literature review (Nag et al., 2019), 60% of the pedestrian LOS models have come through regression techniques and 22% through scoring system techniques. The developed methods can be categorized by the considered parameters; quantitative or qualitative or both categories of parameters (Raghuram Kadali and Vedagiri, 2016). Over the years, there has been a shift from quantitative methods, which have their roots mainly in the USA and focus on flow and density, towards qualitative and mixed methods, which explore the characteristics of the built environment and consider the perceptions of the users. Numerous methodologies and studies have been also implemented for the bicycle LOS, with the efforts having been intensified in the last three decades (Kazemzadeh et al., 2020). These studies have many features in common with those of pedestrians and can easily fall into the same categories. One of the most important and widely accepted methodologies is that of Botma (1995), who introduced the concept of "hindrance", which is expressed by the frequency of events between bicycles. An event is defined as a situation where one cyclist overtakes or meets another.

Botma's (1995) research, in addition to the methodology it proposes for bicycle LOS, also proposes a methodology for determining the LOS in pedestrians-cyclists shared infrastructure and it was the first to be proposed for infrastructure of this type and was the basis for subsequent ones. As in the case of bicycle LOS, his methodology is based on the concept of "hindrance" and consequently on the frequency of events between the users of the infrastructure. It is obvious that in the case of pedestrians-cyclists shared infrastructures, the categorization of events is not only related to the travel direction (i.e. overtaking or meeting), but also to the type of users who interact. The next attempt was made several years later by Hummer et al. (2006), who tried to improve some of Botma's methodology points; i.e. they calibrated and validated a model in conditions that have differences from the conditions in the Netherlands, they included an additional event type, i.e. delayed passing, and they examined various infrastructure widths. A totally different approach was followed by Petritsch et al. (2010), who do not rely on the event types, but they use data about users' perceived LOS from a questionnaire survey and measurements of geometric and functional characteristics of infrastructures. Based on them they develop a linear regression model that quantifies the effect of infrastructure's characteristics on the perceived LOS. Similar approaches with the one of Petritsch et al. (2010) were followed by later studies (Kang et al., 2013; Nikiforiadis and Basbas, 2019), but instead of using linear regression modelling, discrete choice modelling techniques were used, which are more suitable due to the non-continuous character of the dependent variable (i.e. LOS).

2.METHODOLOGY

2.1. METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR DEFINING LOS IN PEDESTRIANS-CYCLISTS SHARED SPACES

This part of the methodology is based on the hindrance concept and more specifically on the events between the users of the shared-use infrastructures, since they express the perceived hindrance. Six event types are being recognized both for pedestrians and cyclists, two of them are related with meetings, three of them are related with passings and there is also a delayed passing event type, which expresses a situation where a user is willing to perform a passing but he/she is not able to do so due to increased congestion in the infrastructure. For the purposes of the methodology presented in this paper, the occurrence of the aforementioned interactions in a radius of less than 1 meter was defined as an event, based on findings of previous studies (Kiyota et al., 2000; Haworth et al., 2014). The shared space LOS, proposed in the present paper, requires the calculation of the total hindrance experienced by the users. To achieve this, it is necessary to estimate the frequency of each event, as well as its significance, represented by weight factors. Concerning the events' frequency, the collection of data in real pedestrians-cyclists traffic situations is needed. This data concerns the geometric (total width, effective width, bicycle lane width, inclination) and functional (volumes and speeds of users) characteristics of the pedestrians-cyclists shared spaces. For estimating events' frequency, the data were analysed using regression trees. Regression tree is a supervised machine learning algorithm that belongs in the decision trees family and it is specifically used for predicting variable that are continuous. These models were evaluated as the best solution after several tests, since they were capable of capturing the non-linear relationship between the variables.

Regarding the weight of each event type, in our knowledge there are no other studies in the literature. In the methodology proposed in the present paper, an analytic hierarchy process (AHP) analysis is proposed in order to assign a weight in every event type. AHP is a multi-criteria technique, that is suitable for quantifying weights of decision criteria based on user responses in pair-wise comparisons. For the present paper, responses were collected by both cyclists and pedestrians. The combination of the events' frequency and weights results in an equation, which defines the total hindrance experienced by a shared-use infrastructure user:

$$Total\ Hindrance = \sum_{i=1}^{12} f_i * w_i \quad (1)$$

where f expresses the frequency of the event i and w the weight of the event i .

2.2. METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR DEFINING QOS IN PEDESTRIANS-CYCLISTS SHARED SPACES

This part of the methodology aims to investigate a research hypothesis regarding the factors that affect the QOS, but also the relationship between these factors. The structural equation modelling (SEM) approach was followed. SEMs can be understood as a combination of confirmatory factor analysis and path analysis (Joreskog and Goldberger, 1975). Factor analysis reduces a set of variables by extracting all their commonalities into a smaller number of factors; these factors are also known as latent variables, i.e. variables that are not directly measured but are inferred indirectly and represent an underlying concept. Path analysis assess the effects of a set of variables acting on a specified outcome via multiple causal pathways. SEM became really popular due to (Schumacker and Lomax, 2016): a) the possibility to investigate relationships between multiple variables, b) the reduction of the measurement errors, c) the possibility to analyse research hypotheses, d) the ease to understand how they work. For the development of the SEMs, the process that was followed is: a) formation of a theoretical hypothesis based on literature, b) exploratory factor analysis for examining if variables related with the qualitative attributes of the infrastructure should form a single or multiple latent variable, c) confirmatory factor analysis for examining the validity of the measurement model, d) structural model formation by defining relationships between variables, e) examination of different models with minor variations in the structural model and evaluation based on the collected data. Two different models are developed, one for pedestrians and one for cyclists. Yet, the theoretical hypothesis that is being formed for the two models is similar:

- LOS has an impact on QOS: the impact of density-related parameters on users' perceived QOS is investigated
- Qualitative attributes of the shared infrastructure have an impact on QOS: the impact of lighting, green areas, urban equipment, traffic signals, attractiveness of land uses, cleanliness, pavement quality, noise and air quality on users' perceived QOS is investigated
- User's profile has an impact on QOS: this relationship examines whether age, gender and user's experience have an impact on the QOS that pedestrians and cyclists perceive
- User's behaviour has an impact on QOS: this relationship examines whether the QOS that a user perceives is affected by his/her behaviour and the behaviour of others
- User's profile has an impact on the assessment of the qualitative attributes: it is investigated if the assessment of the qualitative attributes is different based on user's profile
- User's profile has an impact on the behaviour of the users and on the way they assess the behaviour of others: through this relationship it is investigated if and how the user's profile affect the way they behave, as well as if the user's profile and mainly their experience from using shared infrastructure affect how they assess the behaviour of others. It should be noted that the behaviour of users is self-assessed; yet, their responses can reveal an indication on how they actually behave.

3. METHODOLOGY IMPLEMENTATION

3.1. STUDY AREA

The proposed methodology is applied in pedestrians-cyclists shared spaces in the Municipality of Thessaloniki, Greece. Currently, Thessaloniki is a city with extremely low bicycle usage rates and bicycle use is mainly for recreational purposes (Boufidis et al., 2020). Within the Municipality of Thessaloniki there is a bicycle network of 11.73 km. The present paper does not concern the entire network but it is limited to the part of the network which is placed on sidewalks and pedestrian streets and therefore a pedestrians-cyclists shared space is being formed. Figure 2 presents a snapshot of the examined streets.

Figure 2: a) Aggelaki, b) Ethnikis Amynis, c) Agias Sophias, d) Palia Paralia, e) Nea Paralia

3.2. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR LOS

Prediction of events' frequency

For the prediction of the events' frequency, field measurements were carried out. Field measurements through observers were preferred than video recording, since this method leads to accurate observations and allows the researcher to become familiar with the operational conditions of the infrastructure and the general environmental conditions of the study area. Obtaining an observation included the selection of a pedestrian or bicycle user as a subject of observation, provided that he/she moves approximately linearly from the beginning to the end of a 150 m section, which was defined as the study interval, in each of the five infrastructures. As soon as the selected user entered the study interval, one observer was recording user's travel time in order to compute his/her speed, a second observer was recording user's inclusion in events per category (six categories for each user), and a third observer was recording pedestrian and bicycle flows in a cross section in the middle of the study interval. 310 successful

observations of pedestrians and 289 of cyclists were conducted. For the collected data, various alternatives predictive models were examined, i.e. linear regression, log-transformation of variables, Poisson or negative binomial models. After examining the alternatives, the conduction of a regression tree analysis was chosen and carried out with the tree package (Ripley, 2018) in R programming language (R Core Team, 2013), achieving to capture the non-linearity in the data. It should be mentioned that in different case studies, different modelling approaches may be more suitable.

Pedestrians’ events

From pedestrians’ observations it was identified that two types of events, i.e. being passed by a cyclist and delayed passing, are extremely rare, which is attributed to the low volumes of bicycles in the city. Thus, the frequency of these two events was considered to be equal to zero and the developed models only concern the other four types of events. For the development and evaluation of the regression trees, pedestrians’ database was randomly separated into training and test set (80-20%). Based on the training set, a tree for each of the four event types was created; the algorithm selects for each branch the split, i.e. the variable and the respective threshold, that minimizes the sum of the squared deviations from the mean in the two separate partitions. Then, trees are pruned (optimized) for avoiding over-fitting. The optimal number of terminal nodes was determined based on the cross-validation method by minimizing the mean squared error. The final trees, are presented in Figures 3-6. It should be noted that in the following figures, the acceptance of the condition shown above each bifurcation leads to the left branch, while the rejection leads to the right.

Figure 3: Estimated frequency of “pedestrian meeting another pedestrian” event type

Figure 4: Estimated frequency of “pedestrian meeting a cyclist” event type

Figure 5: Estimated frequency of “pedestrian passing another pedestrian” event type

Figure 6: Estimated frequency of “pedestrian being passed by another pedestrian” event type

The frequency of the events is mainly affected by the pedestrian flow rate. Also, pedestrians’ speed found to be important, but in some cases an increase in speed results in higher frequency, while in other cases results in lower frequency. Bicycle flow rate found to be very important specifically for the “pedestrian meeting a cyclist” event type. Table 1 presents the root mean squared error (RMSE) on the test set for each regression tree. For facilitating the evaluation of the models specific descriptive statistics are also presented, since RMSE is measured in same units as the dependent variable and it is a scale-dependent metric.

Table 1: Evaluation of regression trees for pedestrians’ events

Event type	Mean value	Range	Standard deviation	RMSE
meeting another pedestrian	0.0559	0 - 0.4105	0.0530	0.0398
meeting a cyclist	0.0035	0 - 0.1310	0.0116	0.0114
passing another pedestrian	0.0054	0 - 0.1190	0.0124	0.0186
being passed by another pedestrian	0.0027	0 - 0.1134	0.0107	0.0142

Cyclists’ events

As in the case of pedestrians’ events, from cyclists’ observations, it was shown that two types of events, i.e. being passed by another cyclist and delayed passing, are extremely rare. As a result, the developed models only concern the other four types of events. The trees, which predict the events’ frequency from cyclists’ point of view, are presented in Figures 7-10.

Figure 7: Estimated frequency of “cyclist meeting a pedestrian” event type

Figure 8: Estimated frequency of “cyclist meeting another cyclist” event type

Figure 9: Estimated frequency of “cyclist passing a pedestrian” event type

Figure 10: Estimated frequency of “cyclist passing another cyclist” event type

Pedestrian and bicycle flow rates are the two variables with the greatest impact on the events’ frequency. The speed of cyclists also has a great impact on the frequency of the events. Cyclist speed causes a significant increase in events’ frequency in all cases. Table 2 presents the RMSE of each regression tree, as well as descriptive statistics of the dependent variables.

Table 2: Evaluation of regression trees for cyclists’ events

Event type	Mean value	Range	Standard deviation	RMSE
meeting a pedestrian	0.0637	0 - 0.2500	0.0506	0.0469
meeting another cyclist	0.0171	0 - 0.2400	0.0375	0.0324
passing a pedestrian	0.0405	0 - 0.3500	0.0561	0.0386
passing another cyclist	0.0038	0 - 0.1304	0.0148	0.0146

Estimation of events’ weights

To determine the weights of the different types of events, two questionnaire surveys were conducted, the first addressed to pedestrians (250 responses) and the second one to cyclists (200 responses). The purpose of the two questionnaires was to reveal users’ opinion about the

negative impact of the different types of events on their perceived comfort and safety, in order to assign a weight in each event type using the AHP method (Saaty, 1980). The assessment of the impact of the different types of events was carried out using pairwise comparisons in the questionnaires. Normally, each questionnaire would have to include 15 $((n*(n-1))/2)$, where $n = 6$) comparison pairs. However, following a pilot survey and based on the understanding of previous studies that each person can effectively manage up to 9 comparison pairs, it was decided to reduce the number of pairwise comparisons and to compute the incomplete pairs using the transitive rule ($a_{ij}=a_{ik}*a_{kj}$) (Srdjevic et al., 2014). It was also considered advisable to include a number of pairwise comparisons greater than the minimum $(n-1)$, since a certain amount of redundancy is useful. Thus, 8 pairwise comparisons were included in each questionnaire for keeping a balance between respondent's effort and gained information. The results of the AHP method based on the users' responses are depicted in Tables 3 and 4. The local weight is the one calculated for a single type of user, while the global weight is the half of the local weight, since two types of users exist and all the weights, independently of the user type, are finally integrated in a single equation (equation 1).

Table 3: Pedestrians' weights on event types

Rank	Event type	Local weight	Global weight
1	delayed passing	0.36	0.18
2	being passed by a cyclist	0.18	0.09
3	meeting a cyclist	0.17	0.085
4	passing a pedestrian	0.10	0.05
4	meeting a pedestrian	0.10	0.05
6	being passed by a pedestrian	0.09	0.045

Table 4: Cyclists' weights on event types

Rank	Event type	Local weight	Global weight
1	delayed passing	0.30	0.15
2	passing a pedestrian	0.20	0.10
3	meeting a pedestrian	0.16	0.08
4	being passed by a cyclist	0.12	0.06
5	passing a cyclist	0.11	0.055
5	meeting a cyclist	0.11	0.055

From the results it is noted that Thessaloniki's data do not support Botma's assumption, that passings have twice the negative impact of the meetings. More specifically, passings and meetings create an almost identical hindrance to users, except in the case of cyclist-pedestrian interaction, from the point of view of the cyclist. In this case, passing (local weight: 0.20) is indeed worse than the meeting (local weight: 0.16), because of the fact that the cyclist knows that the pedestrian has no visual contact with him/her. In both cases, users attach greater weight to the events involving users of the other group. Also, it becomes clear that both for pedestrians and cyclists, the delayed passings create the greater nuisance.

Identification of LOS thresholds

In order to identify the LOS thresholds and match the "Total Hindrance" values with LOS values, additional field measurements were made. These were carried out on Sunday afternoon at the Palia Paralia infrastructure, where very high pedestrian and bicycle flow rates are usually observed and during morning hours of a typical weekday at the Nea Paralia infrastructure, where very low pedestrian and bicycle flow rates are usually observed. The purpose of these measurements was to define values for LOS A and LOS F. The intermediate thresholds were determined so that each intermediate LOS value has the same range (see Table 5). During the measurements, all elements included in the regression trees were recorded. Based on the recorded values, the frequency of the events was determined from the regression trees and then the "Total Hindrance" from equation (1). It should be highlighted that the presented matching of total hindrance values with LOS values can't be considered valid for other contexts than that of Thessaloniki and especially for contexts with different traffic characteristics.

Table 5: Expression of "Total Hindrance" values at LOS values

LOS	Total Hindrance
A	≤ 0.0041
B	0.0042 – 0.0109
C	0.0110 – 0.0177
D	0.0178 – 0.0245
E	0.0246 – 0.0314
F	> 0.0314

3.3. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR QOS

Considering the theoretical hypothesis, which was presented in Section 2.2, two similar questionnaires were designed, one for pedestrians and one for cyclists. The data collection made on-site, during peak hours. During the same period also measurements related with the geometric and functional attributes of the infrastructure were carried out for calculating the LOS of each infrastructure in peak hours. In this way LOS and QOS were computed/gathered in similar conditions (i.e. peak hours) and therefore the investigation of the impact that the former has to the latter can be considered valid. It should be mentioned that Likert scales were mainly included in the questionnaires, which are considered suitable for SEM analysis. Likert scales are widely used to measure attitudes and opinions with a greater degree of nuance than a simple "yes/no" question. In total, 489 complete questionnaires were collected, 275 from passing pedestrians and 214 from passing cyclists. Pedestrians' questionnaire was filled by 48.4% males and 51.6% females and the cyclists' questionnaire was filled by 63.1% males and 36.9%.

Pedestrians' QOS

From the descriptive analysis of pedestrians' responses, it seems that most pedestrians consider their behaviour cautious, with 85.5% of them stating that they try to respect the bicycle lane boundaries and 89.1% stating that they are paying attention to passing bicycles. Pedestrians also positively assess the behaviour of cyclists in shared infrastructures. More specifically, 72.4% of pedestrians believes that cyclists try to respect the boundaries of the cycling lane, while the 75.3% believes that cyclists pay attention to pedestrians and the 74.9% that they ride in reasonable speeds. Regarding the assessment of infrastructure's qualitative attributes, it seems that pedestrians are particularly satisfied with the lighting and attractiveness of land uses, while they are dissatisfied with the noise levels, the air quality and mainly the traffic signals in the shared infrastructures.

The questionnaire included the assessment of 9 qualitative attributes. With the aim to investigate whether and how these qualitative attributes can form a single or multiple latent variable(s), exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was performed. The Principal Axis Factoring method was used and the Varimax rotation technique (Fabrigar and Wegener, 2012). The results of the EFA lead to the conclusion that one factor could include the noise and air quality, while a second factor all the other qualitative attributes. This distinction separates the variables that are related with the wider environment of the infrastructure from those that are related more closely with the infrastructure itself. The two factors explain approximately the 40.3% of the total variance, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) indicator is equal to 0.824 (values >0.8 are considered appropriate) and the significance level of Bartlett's test of sphericity is lower than 0.05, indicating that there is a substantial correlation in the data and factor analysis is suitable.

As a next step, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is performed for investigating whether each latent variable is sufficiently expressed by the measured variables. The analysis was carried out in R (R Core Team, 2013) using the lavaan package (Rosseel, 2012). All variables were simultaneously examined and the Diagonally Weighted Least Squares (DWLS) estimation method was used, since it is preferred in case of ordinal variables (Xia and Yang, 2019), especially when they do not follow a normal distribution (Kaplan, 2001). The results of CFA are presented in Table 9. The "green areas" and "traffic signals" measured variables were not used in the final model, since their exclusion resulted in a more powerful CFA model in terms of statistical validity. All z-values are higher than 1.96 showing that all measured variables are important for factors' estimation; for the first measured variable of each latent variable a z-value is not being computed, since the factor loading is a-priori set equal to 1 for minimizing the unknown parameters and increasing the degrees of freedom for achieving a better estimation of the model's parameters. The factor loadings express the correlation of each measured variable with the underlying latent variable.

Table 9: CFA parameters – pedestrians’ model

Latent variables	Measured variables	Factor loadings	z-value
Wider environment	Noise	0.762	-
	Air quality	0.721	11.257
Infrastructure environment	Lighting	0.612	-
	Cleanliness	0.744	11.366
	Urban equipment	0.677	10.676
	Land uses	0.404	6.678
	Pavement quality	0.733	11.175
Experience	Specific infrastructure usage frequency	0.973	-
	Shared infrastructure usage frequency	0.524	3.271
Pedestrians’ behavior	While I walk, I try not to enter the bicycle lane	0.663	-
	When I cross the bicycle lane, I always check for passing bicycles	0.970	3.736
Cyclists’ behavior	Cyclists respect the bicycle lane boundaries	0.609	-
	Cyclists ride in reasonable speeds	0.717	8.488
	Cyclists pay attention in crossing pedestrians	0.652	7.890

The final step of the analysis is to define a valid, in terms of statistical significance and logic, structural model, by investigating alternatives that are closely linked with the already defined theoretical hypothesis. Except of the latent variables that are included in Table 9, the structural model also includes some measured variables that are related with the theoretical hypothesis, i.e. gender, age, LOS. As in the case of CFA, the DWLS estimator was used. The final SEM for the assessment of shared infrastructure from the pedestrians is shown in Figure 11. It should be noted that the latent variables are indicated with ovals, while the measured variables are indicated with rectangles; the values within the diagram are coefficients which indicate how the variables are related. The results show that:

- Factors that affect pedestrians’ perceived QOS: The qualitative attributes that are related with the infrastructure itself, i.e. lighting, cleanliness, urban equipment, land uses, pavement quality, are by far the most influential factor. The important effect of these attributes on users’ perception has been also highlighted by previous studies. Pedestrians’ age also affects the perceived QOS; younger adults are more easily satisfied. The gender and the assessment of cyclists’ behaviour also have some impact; males tend to be more satisfied and the same exists for those that assess positively the behaviour of cyclists. The impact of LOS is not significant, but its inclusion in the model was improving the goodness of fit of the model, showing that an effect on QOS exist. Finally, the qualitative attributes of the wider environment and the assessment of pedestrians’ behaviour are not important influential factors.
- The role of pedestrians’ experience: Despite the fact that pedestrians’ experience did not found to have a direct impact on perceived QOS, it has an indirect impact. This indirect impact stems from the strong relationship between the experience and the assessment of the qualitative attributes; those pedestrians with limited experience assess more positively the

qualitative attributes. Also, it is identified that pedestrians with less experience behave in a more cautious way, i.e. respect the bicycle lanes boundaries and cross carefully the bicycle lanes, and assess more negatively cyclists' behaviour.

- The role of gender and age: As it was already mentioned, gender and age affect the perceived QOS. Yet, they also have an impact on other factors; females behave more cautiously and as the age increases the assessment of cyclists' behaviour is worsening.

Figure 11: SEM for assessing pedestrians' perceived QOS

Cyclists' QOS

Most cyclists assess really positively their behaviour in shared infrastructures; 92.1% state that they try to respect the bicycle lane boundaries, the 94.9% pays attention to crossing pedestrians and the 87% cycles in reasonable speeds. On the other hand, cyclists assess negatively the behaviour of pedestrians (it is recalled that the behaviour of the cyclists had been assessed positively by the pedestrians). The 75.7% shares the opinion that pedestrians are not respecting the bicycle lane, while only 24.3% believe that pedestrians are usually checking for passing bicycles. Cyclists' are mainly satisfied with the attractiveness of land uses, the urban equipment and the lighting, but they are not at all satisfied with the pavement quality and the traffic signals in the shared infrastructures.

The next step of the analysis is to investigate whether and how the 9 qualitative attributes should form a single or multiple latent variable(s), through EFA. The Principal Axis Factoring method and the Varimax rotation technique are being used. From the EFA results it becomes understood that one factor could include noise, air quality and land use attractiveness, while a second factor could include the 6 other attributes. Yet, based on the logical relationship between variables

and for compatibility with pedestrians' analysis it was opted to initially include land use attractiveness in the second factor and to reassess its inclusion there through the CFA. The two factors explain approximately 43.6% of the variance, KMO takes the value of 0.810 and Bartlett's test of sphericity takes a value lower than 0.05, showing that the results of EFA can be considered valid. Table 14 presents the results of CFA. The DWLS estimation method is being used, since the examined variables are ordinal and skewed. Should be noted that this step of analysis shows that the land use attractiveness should be excluded, as well as the cleanliness. All included variables have particularly high z-values and they therefore have an important contribution.

Table 14: CFA parameters – cyclists' model

Latent variables	Measured variables	Factor loadings	z-value
Wider environment	Noise	0.858	-
	Air quality	0.770	8.305
Infrastructure environment	Lighting	0.709	-
	Urban equipment	0.723	12.390
	Green areas	0.602	10.119
	Traffic signals	0.615	10.150
	Pavement quality	0.701	13.146
Experience	Specific infrastructure usage frequency	0.770	-
	Shared infrastructure usage frequency	0.619	2.294
Pedestrians' behavior	Pedestrians respect the bicycle lane boundaries	0.883	-
	Pedestrians always check for crossing bicycles	0.892	9.149
Cyclists' behavior	When I cycle, I try to respect the bicycle lane boundaries	0.782	-
	I always cycle in reasonable speeds	0.859	6.885
	When I cycle, I always pay attention in crossing pedestrians	0.512	6.175

After examining some variations in the structural model, the SEM that is presented in Figure 12 was selected as optimal. The results of this SEM demonstrate that:

- Factors that affect cyclists' perceived QOS: The qualitative attributes of the infrastructure itself, i.e. lighting, green areas, urban equipment, traffic signals, pavement quality, play the most decisive role; on the other hand, the effect of the qualitative attributes of the wider environment on QOS is limited. The second most decisive factor is the experience; cyclists with greater experience from shared infrastructures assess the infrastructure more positively. Cyclists' behaviour has also an important impact in the assessment. Those cycling more cautiously, i.e. pay attention to crossing pedestrians and respect both bicycle lane boundaries and speed limits, perceive a higher QOS. Finally, females tend to perceive a lower QOS. It should be also noted that LOS is not included in this model, since its inclusion wasn't found significant and it wasn't improving the model's performance.
- Cyclists' behaviour: The behaviour of cyclists is related with their experience and characteristics, i.e. age and gender. A more cautious cycling behaviour is observed by older female cyclists, that have limited cycling experience in shared infrastructures.

Figure 12: SEM for assessing cyclists' perceived QOS

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a reliable and easy to implement methodology for assessing pedestrian-cyclists shared spaces, which can be used by transport planners, urban planners, researchers and decision makers. The methodology provides a holistic assessment, by covering both LOS and perceived QOS. A novelty of the proposed methodology is the estimation of the events' weights. From the assignment of the weights in Thessaloniki, it can be concluded that:

- pedestrians feel particularly hindered by cyclists, while cyclists feel particularly hindered by pedestrians. This is probably due to the fact that pedestrians' movement is more unpredictable and in many cases forces cyclists to maneuver. Because of this significant nuisance that each group of users seems to perceive from the other group of users, it is advisable to reduce the friction between pedestrians and cyclists as much as possible. This friction reduction can be achieved by appropriately allocating the available space between pedestrians and cyclists or by clearly separating them.
- in Thessaloniki, passings do not seem to have greater impact on users' perceptions than the meetings, as Botma (1995) had assumed. Passings and meetings create a similar hindrance, except in the case of cyclist-pedestrian interaction, from the point of view of the cyclist.
- delayed passing is clearly the most disturbing situation for both pedestrians and cyclists.

From the prediction of the events' frequency through regression trees, it can be concluded that:

- in the frequency of pedestrians' events, pedestrian flow rate plays a decisive role,
- for the frequency of cyclists' events, apart from the pedestrian flow rate, bicycle flow rate and cyclists' speed have also a strong impact.

The increase in the frequency of all cyclists' events types due to increased bicycle speed demonstrates the importance of moderating the speed of bicycles in pedestrian-cyclists shared spaces. To maintain the speed of bicycles at acceptable levels it is necessary to use appropriate horizontal and vertical advisory signs/markings, as well as to use different pavement material at spots where there is a strong interaction with pedestrians.

The proposed methodological concept aims to be generalized in every pedestrian-cyclist shared space infrastructure, independently of its characteristics. However, in some cases adaptations may be needed. The proposed methodology can be used in three different ways:

- the event weights and the models developed in the present paper can be taken for granted, in case of cities with similar traffic characteristics with Thessaloniki and specifically for infrastructures similar to those explored in this study. This is the most easily applicable case, it is only required to collect data (or to estimate) about pedestrian and bicycle flow rates, pedestrian and bicycle speeds, inclination, and type of segregation.

- taking only the developed models for granted, in case of cities where users have greater experience with shared infrastructures. In this case, except of the collection of the above data, it is also necessary to conduct questionnaire surveys and to apply a weighting method in order to identify possibly different weights for each event type.
- using only the methodology, in case of cities with much higher bicycle flows and more advanced cycling culture and for cities having pedestrians-cyclists shared spaces with significantly different characteristics from those presented in the city of Thessaloniki. In this case, it is needed to collect the required data from the infrastructures, to conduct questionnaire surveys for the assignment of the weights, as well as to develop new models (probably other than regression trees) based on the collected data.

Also, the present paper manages to provide evidence-based answers in specific research questions, using a SEM approach:

- The analysis showed that the qualitative attributes of the shared infrastructures should be distinguished in those related with the infrastructure itself and those related with the wider environment of the infrastructure. The impact of the attributes of the wider environment on the perceived QOS is minor. On the other hand, the impact of the attributes of the infrastructure itself is great; for pedestrians, it is identified that pavement quality, cleanliness and urban equipment are of outmost importance, while pavement quality is the most important qualitative attribute for cyclists.
- Demographic attributes and users' experience have an impact on perceived QOS. Regarding pedestrians, it is identified that younger adults and males perceive a higher QOS. Pedestrians' experience has not a direct impact on perceived QOS, but it has an indirect impact, since those pedestrians with limited experience assess more positively the qualitative attributes of the shared infrastructure. Regarding cyclists, the perceived QOS is not affected by the age, but it is affected by the gender; as in the case of pedestrians, males perceive a higher QOS. Interestingly, one of the most important factors that affect cyclists' perceived QOS is the experience; cyclists that have a greater experience from shared infrastructures perceive a higher QOS, this is somewhat in contrast with the finding for pedestrians where those with greater experience were less satisfied.
- The assessment of pedestrians' behaviour does not affect pedestrians' or cyclists' perceived QOS; this could reflect that cyclists when sharing infrastructure with pedestrians are prepared to adapt their behaviour in the behaviour of pedestrians which is much unpredictable. Yet, the assessment of cyclists' behaviour affects the QOS that both user categories perceive. Those pedestrians that assess cyclists' behaviour more positively perceive higher QOS and the same applies for those cyclists that self-assess their behaviour more positively. This outcome indicates that the co-existence of pedestrians and cyclists requires particular responsibility from cyclists, who are lower in the road vulnerability pyramid.

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